

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP AMONG ECONOMIC GROWTH, REAL EFFECTIVE EXCHANGE RATE MISALIGNMENT AND EXCHANGE RATE REGIME: CASE OF TUNISIA

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Abstract

This work's aim is to investigate the impact of real effective exchange rate misalignment on Tunisian economic growth while also assessing the exchange rate regime option's impact on misalignment from 1985 to 2021 using a simultaneous-equation modeling strategy. According to the analytical outcomes, misalignment has an adverse effect on economic growth, and it is exacerbated in a fixed exchange rate regime. The structure of a country's exchange rate regime, that is prospective to impact its growth over time, indirectly, via its impact on one of the determinants of growth in the economy, like misalignment, distinguishes this study from earlier studies.

Keywords: Economic growth, Exchange rate regime, Misalignment, Real effective exchange rate, Simultaneous-equation modeling strategy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, it is becoming more and more difficult to describe the idea of economic growth (EG). Economists are reflecting on what they think about growth and how economic policy can best be described. However, the reality remains, that sustainable EG is one of the priorities for political and economic leaders in most of nations, with the aim of reducing poverty rates and increasing household living standards.

Additionally, the misalignment of the exchange rate (ER) has an impact on EG. Indeed, [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9] and [10] have demonstrated that poor economic performance results from the real ER's misalignment. Of course, an ER misalignment (an overvaluation) has an adverse impact on tradable goods activities. This can affect the economic equilibrium through a surge of capital and weaken profitability in industries. For this reason, this phenomenon has attracted the attention of monetary and political authorities who aim to improve economic performance and ensure macroeconomic stability [11]. These authorities are questioning the connection between EG and ER misalignment, and the connection between ER misalignment and ER regimes [12], [13], [14], [15] and [16]. Overall, the proof taken from these studies is mixed and inconclusive. As a result, we note the lack of a solid agreement on the nature of this link and the importance of emerging it again.

Motivated by this background, we note that there are not many studies carried out on African nations in common, especially in Tunisia. Moreover, most of the existing studies investigate a bunch of countries, whereas this study will focus on a solitary country.

In summary, this investigation endeavors to respond to two questions:

- For the situation of Tunisia, is the correlation between the misalignment of the real effective ER and EG negative?
- What is the suitable ER regime for Tunisia?

Accordingly, we contribute to answer these questions by using the annual Tunisian data that are available from 1985 to 2021. To do so, we adopted the simultaneous equation model using the two-stage least squares (2SLS) approximation technique. The major findings demonstrate that: (i) EG is negatively linked to misalignment of the real effective ER, in accordance with previous empirical research in other nations. (ii) The intermediate ER regime is a better pilot for misalignment, since it has been with a negative coefficient rather than a fixed ER regime [14].

The article's remaining component is organized as follows. In Section 2, we portray the econometric models and estimation procedures. Empirical results and discussions are reported in Section 3. Section 4 contains the conclusion and policy implications.

2. ECONOMETRIC MODELS AND ESTIMATION STRATEGIES

In this section, we present the econometric models for determining the equilibrium ER and study the correlation between EG, real effective ER misalignment, and the ER regime.

2.1 Equilibrium real ER model

The long-run link between the real effective *ER* and a group of important economic factors is evaluated utilizing a minimized-form of (1) below, which is based on the general *BEER* approach¹ framework [17] and [18].

$$REER_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 PROD_t + \alpha_2 OPEN_t + \alpha_3 INVEST_t + \alpha_4 GOV_t + \vartheta_t \quad , \quad (1)$$

Where, *REER* is the real effective ER, *PROD* is the relative productivity, *OPEN* is the trade openness as a proportion of *GDP*, *INVEST* is the gross fixed capital formation as a proportion of *GDP*, *GOV* is the government consumption as a proportion of *GDP*, and ϑ is error term.

For some variables, it is typical to predict the following signs. The possible Balassa-Samuelson impact is intended to be captured by the variable *PROD*. Assuming that the tradable sectors' productivity is higher than that of non-tradable sectors and that pricing for those sectors is uniform across national borders, the elevation in wages for tradable sectors as a consequence of increased productivity exceeds the rise for non-tradable sectors. The last causes an augmentation in inflation and an appreciation of the *REER* [19]; therefore, a favorable outcome is anticipated. *OPEN*, it is anticipated that increased trade openness will put ascending pressure on the tradable to non-tradable goods' relative price, which will cause the equilibrium REER to depreciate [20]; thus, it is expected to be negative. *INVEST*, it is expected to be negative [21]. *GOV*, is biased toward non-tradables or tradables goods ([21] and [22]); thus, its impact on the *REER* is

ambiguous. We may calculate the misalignment percentage ($\%mis$) using the equilibrium ER determined by (1) as follows:

$$\%mis = \frac{REER - EREER}{EREER} \quad (2)$$

2.2 EG, misalignment, and ER regime estimation model

Based on the studies by [14], [5], [6], [7], [23], [15], [9], [24], [16] and [10], we have chosen a dynamic representation by adopting a simultaneous equation model, represented as follows:

$$\begin{cases} GROWTH_t = a_0 + a_1 GROWTH_{t-1} + a_2 FDI_t + a_3 OPEN_t + a_4 GOV_t + a_5 INVEST_t + a_6 INFL_t + a_7 POPGRO_t + a_8 |MIS_t| + \varepsilon_{1t} \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{cases} |MIS_t|^2 = b_0 + b_1 |MIS_{t-1}| + b_2 INFL_t + b_3 FD_t + b_4 RegimeFixe_t + b_5 RegimeInterm_t + b_6 GROWTH_t + \varepsilon_{2t} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

wherein, $GROWTH$ is the growth rate of GDP annually per capita (in %), $GROWTH_{t-1}$ is the growth rate of GDP annually per capita postponed by one duration (in %), FDI is the foreign direct investment as a proportion of GDP , $OPEN$ is the trade openness as a proportion of GDP , GOV is the government consumption as a proportion of GDP , $INVEST$ is the gross fixed capital formation as a proportion of GDP , $INFL$ is the growth rate of the consumer price index, $POPGRO$ is the population growth rate, MIS is the misalignment, MIS_{t-1} is the misalignment of the real effective ER postponed by one duration, FD is the financial development as a proportion of GDP , $RegimeFixe$ ($RegimeInterm$) is dummy variable chosen as follows: if the nation uses a fixed ER regime, 1; otherwise, 0; (1 if the nation uses an intermediate ER regime, otherwise 0), ε_{1t} and ε_{2t} are the error terms that we assume that they are independent from each other and a_i ($i=0...8$) and b_j ($j=0...6$) are the parameters that we are trying to estimate knowing that a_8 , b_4 and b_5 are the interest coefficients in our study.

Based on earlier research, the misalignment's coefficient is projected to be negative ([25], [21], [4] and [26]). $GROWTH_{t-1}$, it aims to capture the conditional convergence effect, which predicts that, all things being equal, nations with an initially low real GDP per capita manage to increase proportionally faster. Thus, we expect a negative sign of real GDP per capita lagged by one duration on economic growth ([27]). FDI , according to the literature ([28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33]), the expected sign of foreign direct investment's effect on EG is theoretically indeterminate. $OPEN$, the rationale behind including this variable is found in conventional trade theory, which views commerce as a driving force behind economic expansion. It is anticipated that trade openness and EG will have a beneficial link. GOV , its effect is unclear ([21]). $INVEST$ is a significant factor in determining EG. In most circumstances, a high GDP investment rate fuels the economy's strong growth rate. Obviously, theoretically, investment and EG are linked in a favorable way ([34], [35]). $INFL$, according to [36], it has a detrimental influence on EG but a beneficial influence on misalignment. $POPGRO$, this variable can have a negative or

positive influence on EG, based on population structure ([37] found a positive sign, while [34] found the opposite). MIS_{t-1} , the prevalence of misalignment in underdeveloped nations discovered by [38] inspired the lagged dependent variable's inclusion. FD , it is considered as an indicator of the assertiveness of the country's financial structure. Consequently, a high level of advancement in finance has a favorable effect on EG ([39] and [40]), so an unfavorable influence on misalignment is expected. *RegimeFixe* (*RegimeInterm*), misalignment is anticipated to be positively impacted by the fixed ER regime (negatively impacted by the intermediate ER regime).

3. RESULTS OF THE EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

We will first present data (Section 3.1), secondly the findings of the equilibrium ER and misalignment (Section 3.2), and finally, those of the correlation EG, misalignment, and ER regime (Section 3.3).

3.1 Data

The series used in this study consist of annual variations from 1985 to 2021. They come from World Bank databases. Each of the basic statistics (excluding the GDP per capita growth rate “GROWTH”) was converted to logarithms. Table 1 summarizes the descriptive statistics, the mean value, min and max values, and the standard deviation of 41 observations from the time series variables. The findings reveal that the “relative productivity” generates a great value mean of 4.251. According to the standard deviation study, “FDI” is likewise the most explosive parameter, with the maximum deviation of 0.634. “Growth” ranges between -0.019 and 0.079.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Variables	Mean	Std.dev	Min	Max
REER	2.157	0.387	1.954	2.315
PROD	4.251	0.102	3.265	4.897
GROWTH	0.036	0.024	-0.019	0.079
FDI	-3.911	0.634	-5.115	-2.361
OPEN	-0.099	0.129	-0.392	0.134
GOV	-1.753	0.081	-1.861	-1.561
INVEST	-1.470	0.111	-1.698	-1.268
INFLATION	-3.136	0.398	-3.920	-2.497
POP	-4.342	0.398	-4.896	-3.616
FD	-0.437	0.130	-0.664	-0.148
REGIME FIXE	0.057	0.235	0	1
REGIME INTERMEDIATE	0.942	0.235	0	1

For the purpose of obtaining a robust outcome and preventing false regression findings, the series' stationarity is confirmed via the ADF and PP tests. Table 2 summarizes the findings of the unit root test. The outcomes show that all variables are stationary in the first difference, except, "Growth" and "FDI" are stationary at a level.

**Table 2: Unit root testing
Augmented Dickey-Fuller**

Variables	Level		First difference	
	t-statistic	p-value	t-statistic	p-value
REER	-1.845	0.215	-2.784	0.001***
PROD	4.125	0.988	-2.354	0.014**
GROWTH	-6.405	0.000***	-	-
FDI	-3.298	0.022**	-	-
OPEN	-1.505	0.519	-5.376	0.000***
GOV	-0.779	0.813	-7.504	0.000***
INVEST	-1.357	0.592	-4.615	0.000***
INFLATION	-2.315	0.173	-8.228	0.000***
POP	-1.716	0.414	-3.099	0.035**
FD	-2.247	0.129	-6.082	0.000***

Philips-Perron

Variables	Level		First difference	
	t-statistic	p-value	t-statistic	p-value
REER	-1.789	0.456	-2.489	0.000***
PROD	4.158	1	-2.165	0.042**
GROWTH	-6.405	0.000***	-	-
FDI	-3.205	0.027**	-	-
OPEN	-1.641	0.452	-7.415	0.000***
GOV	-0.944	0.762	-7.400	0.000***
INVEST	-1.357	0.592	-4.615	0.000***
INFLATION	-2.277	0.184	-8.129	0.000***
POP	-1.407	0.568	-2.827	0.035**
FD	-2.554	0.111	-6.082	0.000***

Note: ***, **: Rejection of the null hypothesis at 1%, 5% consecutively.

3.2 The equilibrium ER estimate and misalignment

To evaluate the long-run association between the real ER and its first principles and to determine the equilibrium ER, we apply the cointegration technique, given that each parameter forming (1) is integrated of the same order (I(1)).

On the basis of the literature review, different mechanisms have been utilized to identify the number of cointegrating links, for example, the [41] approach, which is depended on the Dickey-Fuller unit root tests, and the [42] approach, which is dependent on two statistics: the eigenvalue test and the trace test. The difference between these two approaches is that the first allows only one cointegration relationship to be obtained. In this paper, we will adopt Johansen's approach.

The value of the trace that tests for the presence of "at most" r cointegrating vectors versus the alternative hypothesis of the presence of "at least" $(r + 1)$ vectors provides the assay for the number of cointegrating associations.

Table 3: Johansen cointegration test findings for the REER model

None	Trace test	Critical value at 95%
$r = 0$	25.548	19.265
$r \leq 1$	12.457	14.786
$r \leq 2$	0.145	7.256

The value of the trace of 25.548 > 19.265 rejects the hypothesis of the existence of at most zero vector at 95% and accepts the alternative hypothesis that there is at least one cointegrating vector. The second value of 12.457 < 14.786 accepts the hypothesis of the presence of at most 1 cointegrating vector and rejects the alternative hypothesis of the presence of 2 cointegrating vectors at 95%. The conclusion would be that, overall, there is a cointegrating relationship, i.e., a long-run association between the variables.

By normalizing with regard to the *REER*, the cointegrating vector takes the following form:

Table 4: Long-run correlation between the real effective ER and its principles

<i>REER</i>	<i>PROD</i>	<i>OPEN</i>	<i>INVEST</i>	<i>GOV</i>
1	0.759 (0.158)	-0.154(0.021)	-0.037(0.011)	0.245 (0.045)
<i>t-stat</i>	4.804	-7.334	-3.364	5.445

Note: Standard errors are in parentheses.

Long-run, the *REER* increases with rising relative productivity and government consumption while falling with rising investment and trade openness. The coefficient of relative productivity, which has the anticipated positive sign and is statistically significant at the 1% significance level, supports the Balassa-Samuelson theory. The detrimental effects of trade openness may be linked to the possibility that trade liberalisation in Tunisia may result in a decrease in the relative cost of non-tradable items compared to tradable ones. For economies with high levels of debt, trade liberalisation may result in a loss of net welfare benefits. These findings are in line with earlier theories and some actual evidence from [43] and [44]. A ten-percentage point rise in investment results in a 0.37 percent real effective depreciation in the ER. While a 10% rise in government consumption results in a 2.45% real appreciation. One argument is that the need for non-tradable items is reflected in government consumption.

The degree of the *REER* misalignment can be calculated using the coefficients in Table 4. To be clear, misalignment is the variation between the *REER* and its equilibrium level, the *EREER*. The latter is provided by the appropriate values made utilizing the estimations in Table 4 and the explanatory variable's long-run values. Some authors (e.g., [4] and [1]) use theory to arrive at such long-run values. However, we believe that such a strategy might be influenced by the perception of each author separately. As a result, we prefer to keep using the Hodrick-Prescott filter and the econometric methodology used throughout the research to distinguish between each variable's permanent and transient components.

Figure 1 describes the obtained misalignment series. In fact, we can easily see that the *REER* overvaluation periods outweigh the periods of undervaluation [45]. This implies that during the study period, Tunisia is globally in a stage of deteriorating competitiveness.

Figure 1: Misalignment of the real effective ER

3.3 The results of the relationship EG, misalignment, and ER regime

Table 5 exhibits the measured coefficients of the model. The empirical findings of (3) showed that the t-values of all variables are near to or greater than 1.96, indicating that all are statistically significant at the 1 %, 5 % and 10 % levels, respectively, except the population growth rate (*POPGRO*). Focusing on our interest variable, misalignment, which represents the deviation's degree of the real effective ER, tends to be negatively correlated with growth. Indeed, when the misalignment's degree increases by 10%, the growth rate of *GDP* per capita decreases by 0.88 %.

This effect is not surprising given the results already obtained by other authors such as [46], [47], [4], [48], [49], [50], [7], [24] and [51]. Moreover, the misalignment of the ER is often linked to overvaluation, which is explicitly evoked in economic performance studies [21]. Therefore, it is unfavorable to tradable goods activities and is considered harmful to EG. The growth rate of *GDP* per capita lagged one period is positive and statistically significant at a 1 % threshold, indicating that it varies in the same direction as the growth rate of the current year's real *GDP* per capita.

This outcome contradicts what [6] and [8] found. Referring to previous studies, we have found that *FDI* is a vital factor in elevating EG [52], because of the carry-over effects it generates on the productive structure of partner countries. Our work's findings show that a 10 % elevation in foreign direct investment translates into a 2 % rise in EG [53]. As for trade openness, this variable impacts significantly and negatively the Tunisian economy's growth. As such, a 10 % increase in trade openness prompts a 0.92 % decline in the real

GDP per capita's growth rate. This result contradicts those found by [4] and [54]. Generally, the trade openness' negative influence is because of the failure of the Tunisian authorities' reforms in terms of openness and financial liberalization (in other words, the presence of several obstructions that forestall free trade between Tunisia and the outside world).

As for government consumption, the findings demonstrate that an ascent in government consumption of 10 % decreases EG by 5.58 %. We can explain this result by the impotence of the part of government consumption devoted to investment. Subsequently, it does not produce a multiplier impact.

This findings is in consistent with that found by [8]. Concerning investment, it contributes positively to the growth rate of *GDP* per capita ([7], [9], [5], [23] and [55]). As such, a 10 % rise in investment contributes to a 1.46 % climb in real *GDP* per capita growth rate. This influence of investment on EG reflects the importance of capital accumulation for Tunisia. For the inflation rate, it weighs negatively on Tunisia's EG, in accordance with theories.

Empirical results of (4) outline the second specification about the effect of ER regime on misalignment. Focusing on our interest variable, the ER regime, it appears that the coefficients linked to the intermediate and fixed ER regimes are statistically significant at the 5 and 10 % levels, respectively. Otherwise, we can conclude that the intermediate ER regime is a better pilot for misalignment because it is associated with a negative coefficient than the fixed ER regime. Indeed, the intermediate ER regime tends to minimize misalignment by 0.71 %, whereas the fixed ER regime leads to increase misalignment by 0.24 %. This result is in line with that noted by [14].

The misalignment lagged by one duration is positive and statistically significant at a 10 % threshold, suggesting a great-level of persistence of misalignment in agreement with the outcomes by [38] and [45]. As such, a 10 % elevation in misalignment from the prior year contributes to a worsening of the gap between the actual real effective ER and its current year equilibrium value of 8.02 %.

This result is in line with that noted in the study by [15]. As for the inflation rate, it is statistically significant at the 5% threshold and contributes positively to misalignment. Thus, a 10 % rise in the inflation rate tends to a 5.13 % increase in misalignment. With respect to financial development, the results reject any significant impact of credit to the private sector relative to *GDP*. This result is compatible with that observed by [15]. At last, the growth rate of real *GDP* per capita is statistically significant at a 10 % threshold and negative, indicating that it varies in the dissimilar direction as the misalignment of the *REER*.

Table 5: Estimates of Simultaneous-Equation Model (2SLS)

Independent variables	Dependent variables	
	GROWTH (3)	MISALIGNMENT (4)
<i>CONSTANT</i>	0.049	0.123
<i>t-value</i>	2.606***	1.025
<i>GROWTH</i>		-0.078
<i>t-value</i>		-1.906*
<i>GROWTH(-1)</i>	0.023	
<i>t-value</i>	1.996**	
<i>FDI</i>	0.200	
<i>t-value</i>	1.760*	
<i>OPEN</i>	-0.092	
<i>t-value</i>	-2.346**	
<i>GOV</i>	-0.558	
<i>t-value</i>	-5.826***	
<i>INVEST</i>	0.146	
<i>t-value</i>	3.088***	
<i>INFLATION</i>	-0.055	0.513
<i>t-value</i>	-1.696*	2.039**
<i>POP</i>	-0.038	
<i>t-value</i>	-0.945	
<i> MIS </i>	-0.088	
<i>t-value</i>	-1.885*	
<i> MISALIGNMENT(-1) </i>		0.802
<i>t-value</i>		8.700***
<i>FD</i>		0.085
<i>t-value</i>		1.294
<i>REGIME FIXE</i>		0.024
<i>t-value</i>		1.856*
<i>REGIME INTERMEDIATE</i>		-0.071
<i>t-value</i>		-2.057**
<i>Adjusted R-Squared</i>	0.887	0.654

Note: ***, **, * significant at 1%, 5%, 10 % consecutively.

4. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This work, which was divided into four sections, aims at shedding light on the hotly debated and contested association among ER misalignment, Tunisia's EG, and ER regime. As such, we have analyzed the effect of ER misalignment on EG and the effect of ER regime on misalignment. To do so, we adopted the simultaneous equation model utilizing annual data over the period from 1985 to 2021.

Our major outcomes reveal that EG is negatively associated with the misalignment of the ER (in line with previous studies conducted by other countries). Moreover, the intermediate ER regime could be a better pilot for misalignment than the fixed ER regime [14].

This has policy implications [56]. Indeed, since the misalignment of the ER impacts negatively the economy, monetary authorities must reduce this misalignment. In terms of ER policy and according to our findings, Tunisia must prepare for a transition to a floating ER regime.

Overall, the findings depicted in this research are fairly strong proof in favor of concluding that *REER* misalignment has negatively affected EG in Tunisia. However, there are critical concerns that should be discussed in the future research. Indeed, it would be appropriate to investigate the effect of ER misalignment on other macroeconomic aggregates, other than EG, such as foreign trade and investment.

5. AUTHOR STATEMENTS

Competing interests: The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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Foot Notes:

- 1) The *BEER* (Behavioral Equilibrium ER) utilizes econometric approach to establish a behavioral correlation between the real ER and common economic parameters.
- 2) Referring to the studies by [14] and [15], the misalignment is taken in absolute values.

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